

Technology and Innovation on Implementation of Mathematics Education in Public Universities in Taraba State case Study Federal University Wukari, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated technology and innovation on implementation of mathematics education in public universities. The research design used was a descriptive survey. The population of the study was 114, which consists of all Lecturers in faculty of Education and Department of Mathematics and Statistics in Federal University Wukari, Nigeria. The sample size was 37 which was obtained using purposive sampling technique in selecting all mathematics education and mathematics lecturers because their population is small. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire. It was validated by measurement and evaluation experts. The instrument has a reliability score of 0.85, which was determined using Cronbach's alpha. To answer the research questions, the mean and standard deviation were calculated, and a t-test was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. The findings of this study among others showed that technology and innovation have positive impact on the transformation of the teaching and learning of mathematics in universities. The study also established that technology and innovation have helped both lecturers and students to carry out mathematics programme effectively. Based on the findings, the study recommends that technology and innovation should be included as part of the teaching methods for presenting mathematical concepts.

Keywords: Technology, Innovation, Mathematics Education, Mathematics Lecturers.

Introduction

Mathematics Education is a key area of focus in school curricula and teacher training programs, centered around the teaching and learning of mathematics. It is also a field of study in universities and colleges of education, where both pre-service and in-service mathematics teachers are trained in the methodologies of teaching mathematics, based on various related topics such as shape, size, quantity, and weight (Charles-Ogan, 2014). Mathematics education spans an individual's entire life, from early childhood to adulthood, due to its importance in developing numeracy skills and enhancing quantitative abilities. The core purpose is to train and certify mathematics teachers in specific teaching methods, covering content that connects mathematics to other fields like science. For instance, mathematics is a requirement for admission to programs in engineering, physical sciences, biological sciences, and other related disciplines at Nigerian universities. Many social science courses, including accounting, economics, banking, finance, insurance, and management, also require a solid foundation in mathematics. This foundational knowledge is essential because

mathematics explains the relationships between numbers and measurable quantities, making it a mandatory subject from primary through senior secondary education (Bassey, 2010).

Mathematics plays a crucial role in everyday life, thanks to the dedication of mathematics teachers. It helps individuals navigate daily tasks like counting, measuring time, distance, and weight, as well as buying and selling products. These activities are part of everyone's routine. Even women who may become homemakers need basic math skills, as they regularly deal with tasks like measuring ingredients, estimating quantities for chores, determining sizes, and calculating costs when shopping or receiving services. In essence, mathematics is an essential problem-solving tool in every aspect of life. Whether in personal matters, family responsibilities, business, economics, medicine, engineering, science, technology, communication, or social issues, math is vital. Therefore, the contributions of math educators are indispensable in preparing individuals for a productive life, helping them keep up with the rapid pace of technological advancements and supporting ongoing societal growth, where innovations in mathematics education play a key role (Sam-Kayode, 2017).

Technology opens up new opportunities to make learning more enjoyable, allowing students to develop collaboration skills through online activities. Technology makes it easier to access information, enables teachers to present lessons in exciting ways, encourages students to learn independently, and helps reduce costs in education (Ramzi, 2014).

For both teachers and students to fully benefit from innovative approaches that can boost productivity in teaching and learning mathematics, they must be ready to move away from traditional methods. As Henry (2014) points out, true innovation happens only when people are mentally prepared for change, which leads to fresh ideas and creative activities in the classroom. Carless (2013) defines innovation as efforts to improve education by introducing something new or different. Innovation often goes hand-in-hand with change, as it involves altering the usual ways of doing things to achieve desired results. In education, this could mean adopting new teaching strategies, like mathematics games, task-based learning, or incorporating technological tools such as computer-assisted instruction. It also includes using alternative assessment methods, like computer-managed instruction in math teaching.

Being an innovative mathematics teacher requires careful thought, creativity, planning, determination, and hard work. It's about not giving up when ideas don't work out as expected, but instead trying again until the desired results are achieved (Boundless, 2016).

The impact of technology on students' performance in mathematics is a topic of considerable discussion and research. Studies indicated that technology-based learning methods, like gamification and interactive software, led to improvements in students' math results (Hillmayr et al., 2020). Technology also allows students to receive instant feedback, helping them correct mistakes and adjust more quickly.

However, technology is not a cure-all for improving math performance (Gómez-García et al., 2020). It can sometimes introduce challenges, such as technical problems, distractions, or a lack of proper training in using the tools. Moreover, technology-based interventions may not work equally well for all students and should be adapted to fit individual learning styles and abilities. The success of these interventions also depends on how the technology is used (Birgin & Acar, 2020). For instance, using technology to complement traditional classroom instruction may be more effective than replacing face-to-face teaching entirely (Zengin, 2018). In conclusion, while technology has the potential to enhance math performance, its effectiveness depends on various

factors, including the quality of the technology, the teaching methods employed, and the specific needs and abilities of the students.

Although many researchers have explored the use of technology to assess students' math skills, they often overlook the role of technology and innovation in mathematics education itself. This study, however, focuses on how technology and innovation are being implemented in mathematics education at universities.

Objectives of the Study

This study was to sought:

1. The impact of technology on mathematics education programme in universities.
2. The impact of innovation on mathematics education programme in universities.

Research Questions:

The following research questions provided guide for the study:

1. What is the impact of technology on mathematics education programme in universities?
2. What is the impact of innovation on mathematics education programme in universities?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers' on impact of technology on mathematics education programme in universities.
2. There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers on impact of innovation on mathematics education programme in universities

Methodology

The research design was descriptive survey. The study was carried out in Federal University Wukari. The study population was 114, which consists of all Lecturers in faculty of Education and Department of Mathematics and Statistics in Federal University Wukari, Nigeria. The sample size was 37 which was obtained using purposive sampling technique in selecting all mathematics education and mathematics lecturers because their population is small. Federal University Wukari was also chosen using purposive/convenient sampling technique. Furthermore, they were accustomed to mathematics and the use of technology and innovation in carrying out mathematics programme in the university for a sufficient amount of time to determine the impact of technology and innovation in implementation of mathematics education in the university. A questionnaire using a four-point Likert-type scale for each topic (Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree) served as the data gathering tool. Measurement and assessment specialists validated it. Cronbach alpha was used to determine the dependability index of the instrument, which stands at 0.84. Scores are allocated according to a scale as follows: 1, 2, 3, 4 for responses SA, A, D, and SD for items classified as negative (-), and 4, 3, 2, 1 for responses SA, A, D, and SD for items classified as positive (+). That means that 2.5 is the average (mean). This was calculated by adding the point scale (4+3+2+1=10) and dividing the total by 4, or 10/4. A mean score of 2.50 or higher was deemed acceptable, whereas a mean score of 2.50 or lower was deemed unacceptable (accepted mean indicates positive impact of technology and innovation, rejected mean indicates negative/ no impact of technology and innovation). The study questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation, and the hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance using the t-test method.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings of the Impact of Innovation on Mathematics Education Programme in Universities.

/N	Description.	Mean	S.D	Remark
1.	The uses of Virtual Math Labs aid the conduct of experiments and simulations in mathematics.	2.72	1.03	Accepted
2.	The use of improvised instructional materials enhances the teaching and learning of mathematics.	3.15	0.93	Accepted
3.	Online Homework Platforms helps Students to submit math assignments online for immediate feedback.	2.78	0.96	Accepted
4.	Uses of Math Apps offer practice exercises and quizzes for effective teaching and learning of mathematics.	2.64	1.07	Accepted
5.	Lecturers are always excited in using innovation to improve the teaching of mathematics.	2.90	1.10	Accepted
6.	The use of GeoGebra makes teaching and learning of geometry, algebra, spreadsheets, graphing, statistics and calculus easier	2.66	0.96	Accepted
	Grand Mean.	2.80	1.01	

Table 2 shows a 2.80 grand mean. This is above 2.50 criterion mean, implying that mathematics lecturers are of the view that innovation helps in effective teaching and learning of mathematics programme in universities.

Research Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers' on impact of technology on mathematics education programme in universities.

Table 3: t-Test result of Male and Female Lecturers on Impact of Technology on Mathematics Education Programme in Universities

S/N	Item	No	x	SD	Df	Calculated value	Table value of t	Decision
1.	Male Lecturers	30	3.68	0.51	35	0.32	2.02	Not significant
2.	Female Lecturers	7	3.02	0.46				

According to the data in Table 3, the calculated value stands at 0.32, falling below the table value of 2.02. Thus, the null hypothesis was upheld. Hence, there is no significant difference between male and female lecturers on impact of technology on mathematics education programme in universities.

Research Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers on impact of innovation on mathematics education programme in universities.

Table 4: t-Test Result of Male and Female Lecturers on Impact of Innovation on Mathematics Education Programme in Universities.

S/N	Item	No	X	SD	Df	Calculated value	Table value of t	Decision
1.	Male Lecturers	30	2.80	0.31	35	0.24	2.02	Not significant
2.	Female Lecturers	7	2.90	0.40				

According to the data in Table 4, the calculated value stands at 0.24, falling below the table value of 2.02. Thus, the null hypothesis was upheld. Hence, there is no significant difference between male and female lecturers on impact of innovation on mathematics education programme in universities.

Discussion of Findings

The result showed that the impact of technology and innovation on implementation of mathematics education programme have been met with enthusiasm by mathematics lecturers and have resulted in notable effective teaching and learning of mathematics in universities. This outcome is consistent with a study by Ramzi (2014) which found out that today students' are surrounded by and rely on visual tools to gather information. With so many distractions competing for their attention, engaging them through traditional teaching methods has become increasingly challenging. As a result, learning materials that align with what students are familiar with such as the internet, video games, and television are more effective in capturing their interest and encouraging their participation, making the learning experience more enjoyable.

Again, the findings found that both male and female lecturers have the same view about the great improvement the use of technology and innovation have brought to the teaching and learning of mathematics in universities, which means the use of technology and innovation in implementing mathematics programme in universities have no regard for gender differences.

Conclusion

The use of technology and innovation have positive impact on implementation of mathematics education in universities. Similarly, there is no gender gap in the use of technology and innovation on implementation of mathematics education among male and female universities lecturers.

Recommendations

The conclusions drawn from this study led to the following recommendations:

1. Technology and Innovation should be acknowledged and considered a major teaching strategy for teaching mathematical concepts.
2. University owners ought to make an effort to buy more technological hardware and software for their lectures and students' usage.

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